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there's
something
science
can do.

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The Trump Administration's Tech Transfer Gambit

Issue/problem

United States Commerce Secretary [Howard Lutnick stated](#) the administration's desire to receive half of the revenue that universities derive from patents developed with federally funded research. In August, the Secretary [sent a letter](#) to Harvard asking for a "comprehensive list of all patents" that were the result of federally funded research and stated his intention to send a similar demand to [the University of California system](#).

Description of the problem

Under the [Bayh-Dole Act \(35 U.S.C. §§ 200–212\)](#), universities retain ownership of patents that are developed with federal funding, creating an incentive for universities to patent and license technology. The Secretary argues that the profits of this research provide no direct return to the taxpayer, and that by repurposing half of those revenues, the government could address deficit and funding concerns in other areas. The Secretary's comments follow the administration's acquisition of [golden shares in US Steel, a 10% equity stake in Intel](#), and [15% of Nvidia and AMD's revenues](#) from chip sales in China.

Results

Most universities [break even or lose money](#) on patenting and licensing. Diverting half of the revenues, without transferring half of the costs, will lower the rationale for universities to engage in technology transfer.

Lessons learned

The implications of the Secretary's position remain undefined but represent a challenge to universities, especially given the worsening funding situation of higher education institutions that already face cuts of between [\\$6.9 and \\$8.2 billion](#). It is also expected that if the federal government seeks equity stakes in start-ups spun off from federally funded research, similar to its new arrangements with well-established companies in the economy, there would be a chilling effect on venture capital investment into the development and commercialization of innovative products and treatment.